

Supplement

List of 900 sites with biomass data representing *Picea* spp. used for the construction of additive models

Country	Species of <i>Picea</i> sp.		Number of sample plots	Range					References
	Engl.	Latin.		Age, yrs	Tree number per ha	Stand volume, m ³ per ha	Aboveground biomass, t per ha	Roots, t per ha	
Austria	Common spruce	<i>P. abies</i> (L.) H.Karst.	11	17-100	561-5500	10-845	18-356	Not available	Klapfenbauer and Buchleitner, 1981; Jonas, 1984
Kazakhstan	Schrenk's spruce	<i>P. schrenkiana</i> F. & M.	20	50-230	244-992	154-384	69-155	Not available	Kharitonov, 1966, 1967, 1971
Byelorussia	Common spruce	<i>P. abies</i>	60	7-110	323-18180	14-673	14-426	1,41-125	Zhilkin, 1966; Maisner, 1970; Boyko et al., 1970, 1975b, 1983; Yurkevich et al., 1971, 1975; Anufrieva, 1976; Richter, 1979; Smirnov, 1971b; Blintsov and Asyutin, 1981, 1983; Sidorovich and Bus'ko, 1982; Bus'ko, 1986; Sidorovich et al., 1985; Valetov, 1988, 1989; Ermakov and Asyutin, 1988.
The Ukraine	Common spruce	<i>P. abies</i>	68	10-214	242-28900	12-872	11-574	3-92	Malinovski and Kolishchuk, 1971; Golubets and Polovnikov, 1975; Chernyavskii, 1975, 1976, 1977; Pasternak and Chernyavskii, 1977; Odinak and Borsuk, 1986; Kalinin, 1983; Lakida and Domashovets, 2009.
Germany	Common spruce	<i>P. abies</i>	100	14-142	284-5128	27-690	31-312	10-85	Dietrich, 1968; Droste zu Hülshoff, 1969; Yildirim, 1978; Ellenberg et al., 1986; Raisch, 1983; Feger et al., 1991; Fiedler, 1983, 1987; Pretzsch et al., 1998; Persson et al., 2000; Scarascia-Mugnozza, 2000; Grote, 2002; Mund et al., 2002.
China	Schrenk's spruce, Jezo spruce, Wilson's	<i>P. schrenkiana</i> , <i>P. jezoensis</i> (Siebold & Zucc.), <i>P. wilsonii</i> Masters,	198	40-350	125-3967	91-1152	57-1438	9-131	Zhang, 1980; Zhang et al., 1980; Wang, Zhao, 2000; Luo, 1996; Ni et al., 2001; Li et al., 1981; Chen B., Chen C., 1980; Jiang, 1986.

	spruce, Korean spruce, purple cone spruce	<i>P. koraiensis</i> Nakai, <i>P. purpurea</i> Masters							
Russia	Common spruce, Siberian spruce, Jezo spruce, Caucasia n spruce	<i>P. abies</i> , <i>P. obovata</i> Ledeb., <i>P. jezoensis</i> , <i>P. orientalis</i> (L.) Link	332	9-230	220- 187000	4-992	7-501	5-89	Koshcheyev, 1955; Orlov, 1951, 1955; Remezov et al., 1959; Rozanova, 1960; Marchenko and Karlov, 1961, 1962; Parshevnikov, 1962; Rodin and Bazilevich, 1965; Kravchenko, 1963, 1964; Utkin and Dylis, 1966; Rudneva et al., 1966; Nesterov et al., 1967; Shadrina, 1968; Timofeyev, 1970; Tarankov et al., 1970; Utkin, 1970; Smirnov, 1971a,b; Zhilkin et al., 1971; Chepurko, 1971, 1972; Abrazhko, 1973; Alexeyev et al., 1973; Ignatenko et al., 1973b; Semenova, 1975; Shcherbakov and Zaitseva, 1971; Vatkovski and Grishina, 1971; Kazimirov and Morozova, 1973; Zaboyeva et al., 1973; Kutaf'yev and Mitrofanov, 1973; Archegova et al., 1975; Vatkovski et al., 1974; Vakurov, 1974a; Zolotokrylin and Nosova, 1974; Krauklis et al., 1975; Pozdnyakov, 1975a; Dyukarev and Rozenberg, 1975; Kozin et al., 1975; Kornyak, 1976; Gusev, 1976; Dylis and Nosova, 1977; Vatkovski, 1976; Mitrofanov, 1977, 1984; Marchenko and Rokjanis, 1978; Chertovskoi et al., 1978; Golovenko et al., 1976, 1981; Pis'merov et al., 1979; Pisarenko et al., 1979; Manakov and Nikonov, 1979, 1981; Gerasimova et al., 1980; Panarin et al., 1980; Lozinov, 1980; Vakurov and Polyakova, 1982a; Opritova et al., 1982; Utenkova and Flyagina, 1983; Falaleyev and Shevelev, 1983; Alesenkov, 1983; Gulbe et

									al., 1986; Onuchin, 1986; Merzlenko, 1986; Kulagina, 1986; Dzebisashvili and Aptsiauri, 1988; Firsova et al., 1989, 1993; Prokopovich, 1995; Bobkova, 1987, 2001; Lukina and Nikonov, 1991; Merzlenko and Shestakova, 1992; Chibisov, 1992; Sapozhnikov et al., 1993; Usoltsev, 1997; Utkin et al., 1997; Babich and Merzlenko, 1998; Solntseva and Kholopova, 2000; Vedrova et al., 2000; Babich et al., 2000, 2004; Pleshikov et al., 2002; Usoltsev et al., 2002b, 2004a, 2007, 2010; Sokolov and Petrov, 2004; Terekhov and Usoltsev, 2005; Bobkova and Tuzhilkina, 2006b; Varaksin et al., 2006; Lyuminarskaya, 2007; Bobkova, 2007; Nagimov et al., 2007; Koshurnikova, 2007; Ryabinin, 2010.
Czechia	Common spruce	<i>P. abies</i>	15	25-123	230-2500	120-713	80-332	8-183	Vinš and Šika, 1977, 1981; Vyskot, 1980, 1981, 1990; Šarman, 1984; Černý, 1990; Persson et al., 2000; Scarascia-Mugnozza, 2000
Sweden	Common spruce	<i>P. abies</i>	15	18-145	544-2285	22-802	25-374	31-65	Tamm and Carbonnier, 1961; Tamm, 1963, 1969; Holmen, 1964; Nykvist, 1971; Nihlgard, 1972; Albrektson, 1980a,6; Persson et al., 2000; Scarascia-Mugnozza, 2000
Slovakia	Common spruce	<i>P. abies</i>	13	20-100	444-718	43-1050	22-460	55-73	Dejmal, 1985; Bublinec, 1986; Kodrik, 1992
Denmark	Common spruce	<i>P. abies</i>	12	15-76	735-8080	99-417	113-194	33-48	Möller, 1946; Persson et al., 2000; Scarascia-Mugnozza, 2000
Norway	Common spruce	<i>P. abies</i>	9	25-35	2400-5312	37-164	32-104	28	Braekke, 1985, 1986; Zheng et al., 2002
Estonia	Common spruce	<i>P. abies</i>	9	40-100	245-1550	34-475	25-274	14-71	Kõlli and Kährik, 1970a; Frey, 1977; Lõhmus and Oya, 1983; Frey and Koppel, 1983; Palumets, 1991
Ireland	Sitka spruce	<i>P. sitchensis</i> (Bong.) Carrière	8	9-47	767-3760	19-812	16-338	13-69	Carey and O'Brien, 1979; Black et al., 2009.

Japan	Korean spruce, Glehn's spruce, common spruce	<i>P. koraiensis</i> , <i>P. glehnii</i> (F. Schmidt) Mast., <i>P. abies</i>	7	30-47	488-2240	193-568	125-255	Not available	Yoshimura, 1967; Satoo, 1971a,b; Saito and Yamamoto, 1980
Latvia	Common spruce	<i>P. abies</i>	5	10-89	612-80000	349-455	197-503	58-120	Rokjanis, 1978, 1981
Great Britain	Common spruce	<i>P. abies</i>	4	14-22	2611-3817	96-250	102-205	25	Mitchell et al., 1981; Ford, 1982
Georgia	Caucasian spruce	<i>P. orientalis</i>	3	88-187	335-1735	226-371	184-330	Not available	Darakhvelidze, 1975.
Belgium	Common spruce	<i>P. abies</i>	2	39-55	1065-1156	282-449	121-201	38-70	Devillez et al., 1973a; Kestemont et al., 1977.
Bulgaria	Common spruce	<i>P. abies</i>	3	90-120	385-610	579-1000	279-478	58-119	Grozeva et al., 1986; Antonov, 1991.
Lithuania	Common spruce	<i>P. abies</i>	2	50-60	Not available	200-384	116-217	29-80	Bumblauskis, 1996; Yanushene, 1975
France	Common spruce	<i>P. abies</i>	2	85-92	475-568	614-900	263-428	45-62	Ranger et al., 1992; Persson et al., 2000; Scarascia-Mugnozza, 2000
Italy	Common spruce	<i>P. abies</i>	1	38	1197	345	165	58	Masci et al., 1998; Persson et al., 2000; Scarascia-Mugnozza, 2000
Finland	Common spruce	<i>P. abies</i>	1	250	550	125	97	38	Havas and Kubin, 1983

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